

The Execution of an Animated Mascot as a Marketing Tool

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Abstract: This research aims to fathom the audience attraction and audience-profiling mechanisms employed by animation in commercials. The study examines the function of animation in advertising, which has evolved and emerged from various perspectives. No longer are animation and cartoons exclusively for children's entertainment. This study examines how marketers and advertising agencies use mascots for animated product promotion in advertising. Additionally, the research investigates the two different brand mascots that were animated in a highly inventive manner. The study's research type and methodology were informal and quantitative, respectively. The study focused on a relatively small subset of the population: former viewers of television, internet videos, television advertisements, and YouTube videos.

Keywords: Corporate, Mascot, Animation, Advertisement, Cartoon.

Introduction

The obsolete and outmoded old methods of advertising are no longer used, and supply and demand determine marketing strategies. Advertising cannot effectively promote brands or products (Definition of Advertising, n.d.). (Callot & Lee-Na-Lee, 1994) To attract consumers, advertisers and certain creative individuals seek out additional characteristics that have become well-known and divine. In addition, people's preferences, expectations, and methods of thinking about advertising have evolved, making it imperative that advertisements offer a diversity of concepts and plots. In this situation, animation becomes the most pervasive or conspicuous aspect of advertising. The use of animation in advertising has expanded in a variety of contexts. The public rapidly adopted this multimedia component and received overwhelmingly positive feedback due to advertising.

Public opinion also favors using animated characters in advertising, particularly talkative ones (Tanvir & Arif, 2012). Today, animation has evolved into a highly adaptable and dynamic advertising platform, enabling businesses to implement any concept. David and Sabrina (2004). When it comes to mascots, however, animation provides a far superior execution characteristic for displaying the fictional character in a more lively and affable manner. A mascot typically has a positive impact on a brand or business. However, when consumers discover mascots with radically different dispositions and optimistic outlooks, everything changes for that brand or business in advertising. Through animation, a gorgeous fictitious character created to represent or illustrate the vision and objectives of a corporation or brand has been transformed into a pleasant, appealing, and endearing figure for all individuals.

Moreover, only animation makes it possible. Now that the previously immobile, static graphic, shape, or figure can jump, dance, smile, and converse, it is simpler for consumers to understand the advertisement. In addition, creative individuals have begun using the Mascot in highly original and distinctive advertising by employing animation.

Research Objectives

- This study's primary objective is to investigate how animation is utilized in television advertisements to depict any brand or company's avatar.
- The study also examines how animated mascots in television advertisements help advertisers develop effective marketing strategies.

Methodology

A qualitative research method was employed in this investigation to gain a deeper understanding of the concept of advertisers using animation to promote avatars in television advertisements. The study also investigates how two distinct companies' animated avatars are utilized in television advertisements. The research meticulously develops the rationale behind creating effective marketing campaigns utilizing animated avatars. For this strategy, the study employs both primary and secondary data. The primary source of information was television advertisements for Duracell Battery and Pillsbury, while secondary sources included books, periodicals, etc. To comprehend the value of using animation to illustrate television personalities. To comprehend the value of using animation to portray mascots in television commercials, the research also concentrates on a case study of television commercials for Duracell and Pillsbury.

Analysis

The company moniker Duracell was first used in 1920. Duracell is the most successful alkaline battery brand, according to Smith (2017).

According to Chris Smith's study, Duracell's success can be primarily attributed to its years of market knowledge, skillfully and strategically crafted advertising, and industry experience. Duracell is the foremost expert in batteries and battery technology globally. Duracell is not only an expert at producing alkaline batteries but also a well-known brand for fueling a variety of electrical devices. In 1970, Duracell created its most recognizable character as its emblem to establish its brand identity further. The "Duracell Bunny" was a prominent anthropomorphic pink rabbit in popular culture. This rabbit represents the battery's vigor, the force it exerts to activate the device, and its endurance. The rabbit holds a fixed battery — the Duracell product — on its back, demonstrating its durability. In advertisements or television commercials, the fictional Duracell Bunny is portrayed as a rival, competing against other bunnies (representing other brands) in various scenarios, such as a football game or rock climbing competition. The advertising has utilized the Mascot in an inventive manner. Inside is

It is highly inventive how the advertisers in these commercials used bunnies to represent various businesses to emphasize the Duracell Battery's main USP, its power durability. In the advertisement, rabbits pursue the Duracell Bunny, but when they run out of energy, another rabbit enters their marathon-like pursuit. This diagram depicts how standard battery functions when depleted, and users must purchase a new one to continue using their devices. Duracell Bunny wins the race because the other rabbits are too exhausted to capture him. The bunnies from the other brands have exhausted all their energy attempting to catch up to the Duracell Bunny (a standard battery), constantly racing and winning. It is incredibly

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This suggests that the Duracell Battery has a lengthy lifespan, whereas the consumer must replace nearly 12 batteries of other brands. Television advertisements and other publications acclaim the durability of Duracell batteries due to their alkaline composition. These television advertisements accelerate the propagation of the market and demand for Duracell batteries. In addition to the narrative, the animation in the television advertisements for Duracell batteries is a significant factor in this phenomenon. Without animation, giving this innovative idea a real-world appearance would have been difficult. The only way to bring this company's emblem, the Duracell Bunny, to life

a device that operates on alkaline batteries. It lasts longer because Duracell batteries power it. The brand's emblem is a battery-powered device that also represents the durability and longevity of the Duracell battery. This rabbit exhibits quickness, cunning, and activity, which has a positive psychological effect on observers or consumers. In television advertisements, the Duracell Bunny has assumed a variety of personalities in order to contend with other rabbits that symbolize other products or corporations on the market.

2003 television advertisement featuring narration and a race of sprinting rabbits. In contrast, television advertising focuses on the efficacy of the Duracell Battery compared to competing zinc-air batteries. The depiction of the rabbits in the television advertisement, which represent another brand, was quite unusual. The bunnies from the other brands have exhausted all their energy attempting to catch up to the Duracell Bunny (a standard battery), constantly racing and winning.

and into action is through animation. Using animation, sometimes stop-motion animation, and sometimes 3D animation, the advertiser has presented this rabbit with various notions and concepts. In the accompanying advertisement, Bunny is depicted as a competitive percussionist. In this television advertisement, however, Duracell Bunny is portrayed as a fierce mascot who engages in musical combat with twelve gorillas who represent zinc batteries and overcomes each one individually. The unique selling proposition of this product is described in the advertisement as follows: "You all know that Duracell batteries last longer than leading zinc batteries, but exactly how much longer?" (youtube.com).

Additionally, the advertisement was created using 3D animation. Advertisers have numerous options for animation, so they come up with these concepts and effectively illustrate them (Organ, 2011). In December of 2018, on the YouTube channel for Duracell India, new television advertisements for the Christmas holiday were just uploaded, and this time Bunny is not at all featured competitively. In this instance, the advertiser also introduced Santa Claus and the concept of providing gifts on

Christmas Eve to well-behaved children in their homes. Santa is depicted entering a home through the fireplace's chimney, placing gifts inside, and then departing after realizing that someone else had also entered the home through the chimney.

The second character is Bunny, who enters the house bearing a satchel and dashes toward Santa's stored products. After disassembling the gift package and inserting a Duracell alkaline battery into the device, Bunny extracted it. Advertisers attempted to convey that the modern Christmas celebration would be incomplete without Duracell Batteries. It has also been implied that the influence of devices, electronics, and entertainment is pervasive in contemporary society. This comprehensive Duracell Bunny campaign (Organ, 2011) has substantially impacted the promotion, success, and effective marketing of Duracell Batteries.

Through an analysis of these commercials, the function of animation in the advertising industry has been investigated. Any advertiser or artist can now present their eerie ideas to the public thanks to

He merely grasps his midsection and chuckles. As a result of his popularity among several generations of television viewers, he sells millions of cans of rolls, biscuits, and toaster delicacies and brightens countless individuals' faces. In a television advertisement from 1965, this Doughboy first appeared. This figure, known in Chicago as "Doughboy," was created by Rudy Perz (Hunt, 2015). It has a distinctive quality, as evidenced by the chef's cap on its head, the white cloth around its neck, and the "Hi! The animation transforms me into Poppin' Fresh, the Pillsbury Doughboy. The chef's headwear features the Pillsbury logo. Customers in the United States praised Pillsbury and its television advertisement.

This Mascot's most significant selling point is its adorable appearance. According to numerous theories, soft dolls and endearing characters are extremely popular among women. The Doughboy was another example of how Pillsbury targeted the preponderance of female homemakers using the same strategies. This Doughboy has made numerous appearances and garnered attention as a dancer, rap artist, opera singer, and more. Moreover, due to the animation, all of them became possible. This lends life to the fictional character Doughboy. Initially, it was projected using clay animation (stop-motion animation), but technological advancements have significantly enhanced these endearing minuscule mascots' aesthetics, characteristics, and appearance. The most fascinating aspect of the animation, however, is the gesture made by the housewife as she prods the Doughboy's happy spot. The Doughboy was also awarded this prod as a reward.

This is the most conspicuous USP for Pillsbury's product quality. It reflects and represents the reliability of the company's high-quality, grain-based products, where obtaining the populace's or clients' confidence is the greatest challenge. In contrast, this Mascot has achieved this feat

animation. Animation assists the advertiser in augmenting aesthetic value, and these types of visualizations expand the pondering and imagination of the target audience.

Animation is not a limitation on the capacity to morph or construct films. Several businesses, such as Duracell, use animation to attract their target market and consumers. Sometimes, advertisers and businesses prefer animation to create advertisements and commercials published on their websites and social media platforms such as Facebook and YouTube. It functions as the emblem and promotional symbol for the Pillsbury Company. Although this Mascot's moniker is "Poppin' Fresh," he is commonly known as the "Pillsbury Doughboy." This Doughboy, wearing a chef's cap, is a small, fragile mass of dough selling the product for over four decades. In addition, he is well-known for creating the endearing "Hooo Hooo" sound and for being finger-taunted. He is an optimistic spokesperson who is entirely devoid of malice. Even when the feared finger, which repeatedly jabs him in the midsection, pokes fun at him.

exceptionally by employing a particularly endearing gesture that has garnered immense popularity and developed its supporter base among the audience. In this case, animation is the only way to surmount the challenges of real-world situations; without animation, a fictional character would be unable to sell any products in the advertising and marketing industry and capture the affection of the target audiences. Doughboy is flourishing in over thirty countries and offers an extensive selection of products, from wheat flour to frozen pizza. The Pillsbury Doughboy continues to be regarded as a helpful and friendly companion by chefs of all types, and this is all due to the power of animation. The most significant advancements in the real world can be observed in the creative sectors, where ideas are executed or displayed effectively by employing the correct techniques. Aside from these contexts, animation provides fantastic options and features that meet all the requirements of creative individuals seeking to convey their creative ideas in highly respectable ways.

Conclusion

It is more creative and adaptable to use animation to portray mascots in commercials to

reach the target demographic. Advertising and the company itself can utilize mascots in a variety of methods to communicate the USP, vision, and mission of a business. Companies and advertisers prefer to use mascots rather than personalities to promote their products for obvious reasons. In addition, by using animation, advertisers can construct highly sophisticated marketing strategies that are frequently effective. Moreover, animated mascots are less expensive than prominent endorsements. In addition to breathtaking visuals, animated mascots or characters have excellent communication qualities that attract audiences and leave a profound, partial impression on them. Consequently, the animation-based mascot marketing techniques devised by advertisers are pretty compelling.

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